

Holistic Capacity Building for Open, Distance and Online Learning
***Preconference Keynote on January 28, 2026 at the International Conference organised
by the University Delhi from 28-31 January 2026, New Delhi.***

Thank you for the kind introduction. At the outset my sincere thanks to the organisers for the honour to speak before distinguished guest and participants of the pre-conference workshops. Organizing such an event is a huge effort, and I must thank the senior management of the University of Delhi (my alma mater), and the organizing team for their efforts in curating this event with love and care.

While the conference covers a broad theme of Open, Distance, Digital and Blended Learning, the pre-conference workshops are focused and are intended to provide a deep dive into the respective themes, such as holistic and authentic assessment, learner engagement, disruptive technologies, and development of learning materials. I have worked on these areas over the last 30+ years and have a lot to say. But I would like to be brief as you have experts facilitating the workshops. Fortunately, I had the privilege to work with most of them in conducting similar workshops in the past. So, I am sure you will have very rich and engaging sessions throughout the day.

Let me touch upon the theme to trigger further discussions. Let's understand the central theme of distance and online learning. As primarily asynchronous in nature, the learning materials are central to teaching and learning. Developing high quality materials that are suitable for self-learning forms necessary ingredient for quality education. Whether it is print-based self-learning materials or digital materials, the learning materials must be self-explanatory, self-directed, self-motivating, self-evaluating, and self-contained. This means the SLM we provide to the learners must be prepared in a way that facilitate learning. The learner must feel motivated to learn the content; it must support self-directed learning; it must be written in conversational style to explain the content from known to unknown; it must allow the learner to know how they are progressing by providing appropriate and timely feedback; and finally, the learning materials must be complete so that the learner does not spend extra time searching and finding additional materials. In order to write good and effective SLM, you must have expertise on the subject and also you need to be a good teacher. Learning designers can help you refine your work, and further use technologies to make the learning

materials attractive and engaging. This leads to two important areas covered by the pre-conference workshops – engagements and disruptive technologies.

Technologies are essential part of distance and online learning. From the perspective of definition, distance education is considered technology mediated. Technologies have helped transform correspondence education to distance education. Thus, technologies have played the disruptive role from the first generation of distance education to the fifth generation. According to James Taylor, the fifth generation is about intelligent flexible learning. Moving beyond the use of audio and video, interactive television, and web-based learning materials, the use of Artificial intelligence and big data can make learning personalised. Use of big data and learning analytics create dashboards for learners to identify their pain points, where more efforts may be needed to develop mastery. Gen AI tools can help provide every learner a personalised tutor on their mobile phones. You will explore some of these disruptive technologies in the workshop.

Technologies, also help us to improve the learner engagements. In fact, student engagement is one of the most widely misunderstood area in the field of education. Especially, it is understood primarily as ‘presence’ of student and teacher in a physical location. Traditionally, interaction is considered essential for learning. In the context of the digital environment, there is another aspect, which is ‘interactivity’ of the online systems. Both interaction and interactivity form the basic foundations of student engagement in learning. Michael Moore offered three types of interaction in distance education: student-teacher interaction (which may happen in occasional counselling, and through tutorial in print), student-student interaction (occasional meetings and study groups), and student-content interaction. The student-content interaction is dependent upon how well the SLM is prepared. Borje Holmberg called this ‘guided didactic conversation’. Interactivity of the system is focused on its ability to respond quickly to student inputs and provide relevant responses. For example, use of a discussion forum allows students to interact amongst themselves and also interact with teachers, and therefore the system is also interactive, and create a sense of ‘belongingness’ in the learner. It is also important to note that engagement is not just about the types of interaction and the interactivity of the system, it is about

cognitive, behavioural, and emotional aspect of learning. Thus, in order to have good student engagement, the Community of inquiry provides a good frame consisting of teaching presence, cognitive presence and social presence. In essence, good engagement is about good learning design; and quality student engagement leads to successful learning.

What is successful learning? How do we assess the quality of learning. This will be the focus of another preconference workshop on holistic and authentic assessment. The issue of assessment is very sacrosanct to teachers and educational institutions. How do we assess, and how do we certify learners have so far been the benchmark of quality. The Covid-19 pandemic shattered several myths about assessment, when educational institutions were forced to adopt alternative forms of assessment, including open book assessment to test learner performance. With the rapid progress of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) tools, the nature of assessment has been further questioned, especially whether to allow students to use GenAI to prepare their assignments and reports used for grading and marking. In the distance education system, we have been promoting the use of authentic assessment, including the use of portfolio and real-world work experiences from the beginning. Operationally, use of authentic assessment is complex and time consuming for both the student and the educational institutions. So, unfortunately, either the assignments are made optional or even reduced in numbers. It is important to understand the philosophy of the assignments in distance and online learning. The assignments are learning tools. They are another way of student engagement. They help student identify their strengths and weaknesses and prepare them for real work environments. As teachers, it is our responsibility to ensure that student assessments are comprehensive and serve the purpose to ensure confidence of the employers.

By now, you may have realised that the four workshops are inter-related and inter-dependent. In order to develop quality distance and online learning, all the stakeholders -- teachers, administrators and technical staff must understand the philosophy, principles and practice. I hope there is a good mix of different stakeholders in the workshop to provide in-depth discussion and understanding.

I wish you very best.